

CORDEX-FPSCONV on ESGF

CORDEX-FPSCONV simulations providing some data on ESGF as of **2024-11-21 18:42 UTC**. The full list of variables can be obtained from [here](#).

domain	model	experiment	driving_model	ensemble	model_version	institution	status
ALP-3	AROME41t1	evaluation	ECMWF-ERAINT	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	CNRM	published
ALP-3	AROME41t1	historical	CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	CNRM	published
ALP-3	AROME41t1	rcp85	CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	CNRM	published
ALP-3	CCLM5-0-15	historical	MOHC-HadGEM2-ES	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	CLMcom-DWD	published
ALP-3	CCLM5-0-15	rcp85	MOHC-HadGEM2-ES	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	CLMcom-DWD	published
ALP-3	CCLM5-0-9	evaluation	ECMWF-ERAINT	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	CLMcom-CMCC	published
ALP-3	CCLM5-0-9	historical	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	r12i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	CLMcom-CMCC	published
ALP-3	CCLM5-0-9	rcp85	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	r12i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	CLMcom-CMCC	published
ALP-3	COSMO-crCLIM	evaluation	ECMWF-ERAINT	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	CLMcom-ETH	published
ALP-3	COSMO-crCLIM	historical	MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	CLMcom-ETH	published
ALP-3	COSMO-crCLIM	PGW-MPI-rcp85	ECMWF-ERAINT	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	CLMcom-ETH	published
ALP-3	COSMO-crCLIM	rcp85	MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	CLMcom-ETH	published
ALP-3	HCLIM38-AROME	evaluation	ECMWF-ERAINT	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	HCLIMcom	published
ALP-3	HCLIM38-AROME	historical	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	r12i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	HCLIMcom	published
ALP-3	HCLIM38-AROME	rcp85	ICHEC-EC-EARTH	r12i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	HCLIMcom	published
ALP-3	RegCM4-7	evaluation	ECMWF-ERAINT	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	ICTP	published
ALP-3	RegCM4-7	historical	MOHC-HadGEM2-ES	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	ICTP	published
ALP-3	RegCM4-7	rcp85	MOHC-HadGEM2-ES	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	ICTP	published
ALP-3	WRF381BB	evaluation	ECMWF-ERAINT	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x1n2-v1	FZJ	published
ALP-3	WRF381BG	evaluation	ECMWF-ERAINT	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x1n2-v1	AUTH-MC	published
ALP-3	WRF381BI	evaluation	ECMWF-ERAINT	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x1n2-v1	UCAN	published
ALP-3	WRF381CA	historical	SMHI-EC-EARTH	r12i1p1	fpsconv-x1n2-v1	FZJ-IDL	published
ALP-3	WRF381DA	evaluation	ECMWF-ERAINT	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x1n2-v1	BCCR	published
ALP-3	WRF381DA	historical	NCC-NorESM1-ME	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x1n2-v1	BCCR	published
ALP-3	WRF381DA	historical	SMHI-EC-EARTH	r12i1p1	fpsconv-x1n2-v1	FZJ-IDL	published
CAN-1	COSMO-crCLIM	evaluation	ECMWF-ERAINT	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	CLMcom-ETH	published
CAN-1	COSMO-crCLIM	PGW-MPI-rcp85	ECMWF-ERAINT	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	CLMcom-ETH	published
REU-3	COSMO-crCLIM	evaluation	ECMWF-ERAINT	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	CLMcom-ETH	published
REU-3	COSMO-crCLIM	PGW-MPI-rcp85	ECMWF-ERAINT	r1i1p1	fpsconv-x2yn2-v1	CLMcom-ETH	published